

21st CENTURY LEADERSHIP SKILLS OF SCHOOL HEADS AND PERSONALITY DEVELOPMENT OF TEACHERS: ELEMENTS OF EFFECTIVE PEDAGOGY

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ABSTRACT

Both public and private schools in the country continue to experience rapid and regular changes in their curricula. These changes require teachers to possess the skills and knowledge to implement curricula. In addition, adopting new curricula requires teachers to feel confident in delivering and purpose of the materials they use to ensure accurate implementation. This study aimed to analyze the 21st Century Leadership Skills of school heads and personality development of teachers as determinants of effective pedagogy of teachers. The respondents of the study were 220 elementary school teachers in the seven public central elementary schools in the Division of San Pablo City. The study used descriptive correlational research design to identify the 21st-century leadership skills that predict effective pedagogical skills. The questionnaire via google form was used as a data-gathering instrument. The statistical tools used in the study included frequency, percent, mean, standard deviation, Pearson product-moment-correlation coefficient, and multiple regression analysis to analyze the data. The salient findings are summarized as follows: Both the perceived 21st-century leadership skills of the school heads in terms of flexibility and adaptability and the teacher's personality development were significant predictors of the teachers' strategies and techniques as a measure of their effective pedagogy skills. Result also shows that learners need to be capable of constantly adapting and constantly learning and growing, of positioning themselves and repositioning themselves in a fast-changing world. The study suggested that the kind of teaching strategies needed today in the 21st century requires teachers to be high-level knowledge workers who constantly advance their professional knowledge and that of their profession by continuing to develop themselves by continuous studying and continuous learning.

Keywords: 21st leadership skills, effective pedagogy, curriculum and instruction, strategies and techniques